

Electrospun polycaprolactone membranes doped with bioactive glass nanoparticles for tissue regeneration

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ABSTRACT

Bioactive glasses (BGs) continue to attract interest for applications in hard tissue engineering for replacement, regeneration and repair bone and teeth. Their application possibilities have covered also the area of soft tissue engineering (angiogenesis, cardiac, lung, nerve, gastrointestinal tissue regeneration) and wound healing^[1]. BGs are often incorporated into a polymeric matrix to produce composite which can act as a scaffold or nets for cell adhesion. Biodegradable composite offers a suitable environment for later differentiation, proliferation of the cells and stimulate direct tissue formation *in situ*^[2]. The main aim of this work is synthesis of bioactive glass particles, which are subsequently incorporated to PCL-fibres to create multifunctional membranes for tissue regeneration. Well dispersed spherical nano-sized mesoporous glasses (130 ± 10 nm) based on the binary SiO₂-CaO system were synthesized by using a microemulsion-assisted sol-gel approach^[3]. After comprehensive characterization (SEM-EDS, XRD, FTIR, TEM, BET, bioactivity and cell viability tests), BGs were used for nanocomposite fabrication. The fibre membranes were fabricated by electrospinning method. Biodegradable poly ϵ - caprolactone were used as a polymer matrix. The small size of BGs particles allowed their incorporation into the fibers all over the fiber length. After immersion in simulated body fluids the membranes showed ability to form hydroxyapatite. The obtained bioactive materials have the potential for application in regenerative medicine.

Keywords: bioactive glass, electrospun membranes;

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